

tal area, whereas South America and Africa rank second and third, respectively (see table). Of the six regions, Oceania has the smallest growth rate of land use and total area. If past patterns continue, global rough rice production would increase with an annual rate of 9,790,950 t, largely driven by Asia's growth rate (8,926,580 t y⁻¹) and prevailing production. South America and Africa would share similar annual growth rates and production expectations in rough rice production (see table), while Oceania would hold the least annual growth rate and proportion of rough rice production. With values of 9.88 t ha⁻¹ and 0.091 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹, Oceania has the largest yield expectation and annual growth rate in the six regions, followed by North and Central America. With its predominant proportion in rice production, Asia would yield a similar production forecast in 2025 (5.41 t ha⁻¹) and annual growth rate (0.057 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹) with the world (5.32 t ha⁻¹ and 0.055 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹, respectively). Global annual pesticide sales would continually increase at the annual growth rate of \$163.52 million (see table). The global increase in annual herbicide sales (\$59.57

million y⁻¹) is the fastest compared with sales of insecticide (\$47.29 million y⁻¹) and fungicide (\$41.43 million). By 2025, global rice pesticide sales would reach \$8,577 million.

If past patterns continue, area, production, yield, and pesticides of rough rice for the world, Asia, America, Europe, Africa, and Oceania would increase at constant annual growth rates. Asia is the rice production center in the world and this continent would determine the future trend of global rice production. South America and Africa would remain second and third in production, yield, and annual growth rate of rough rice. Oceania would continue to hold the highest yield in the next 20 years. The global need for rice herbicide was larger than that for insecticide and fungicide and this trend would remain in the future. Habitat destruction and pesticide use in rice production cause environmental degradation or affect human health (Altieri 1994, Heong and Escalada 1998, Tilman et al 2001). Advances in rice science and technology and sound policy decisions are needed to avoid these outcomes.

With advances in technology and in societies, however, these

patterns could change and future intensification of rice production could deviate from what is predicted. Further forecasts may be conducted with more dependent and independent variables taken into consideration.

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Farmer participatory learning on integrated crop management of lowland rice in Mali

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The African rice gall midge (AfRGM) *Orseolia oryziivora* Harris and Gagné and rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) are principal biotic constraints to the sustainable intensification of rainfed

and irrigated lowland rice, posing the most serious challenge to human endeavors in West Africa (Nwilene et al 2002). Considerable progress has been made to control both stresses through

integrated pest management (IPM) components. But, there has been no focus on farmers' needs, knowledge, and capacity for learning ways of managing pest and disease problems under

locally observed conditions (Defoer et al 2004). Often, farmers are handicapped because they lack a basic understanding of pest and disease symptoms, ecology, natural enemies, development patterns of crops and pests, appropriate control measures, soil condition and its effect on the crop, and the effect of weather conditions on pest populations and disease incidence. They do not understand pest resurgence and the reasons for not using insecticides indiscriminately. There is a growing realization that future agricultural growth hinges on smallholder farmers, who must be knowledgeable and exposed to a learning process that involves continuous observation and feedback from the local environment and that enhances decision-making capacity. This paper reports efforts made to train lowland rice farmers on crop management practices and IPM options to enable them to carry out their own experiments on their own farms.

Studies were carried out in two rice-cropping systems of Mali—the rainfed lowland rice system in Sikasso and the irrigated rice system in Niono. Fifty farmers (31 men and 19 women) participated in the learning and training activities (30 farmers from three villages in Sikasso and 20 farmers from two villages in Niono). A number of criteria were used to select the farmer participants: residence in one of the selected villages, experience in rice cultivation, gender (number of active males and females), availability to participate in training sessions, and possession of an easily accessible field. A training manual, prepared in the local language (*Bambara*), was given to participating farmers. A questionnaire was developed to elicit

information on production constraints and farmers' perceptions, local knowledge, and practices. Before the training exercise, all constraints listed by the farmers were summarized and elucidated on, giving technical explanations and practical advice for a better understanding of each problem. Some key indicators to assess farmers' performance were used before and after the training as well as to compare trained (participating) with untrained (non-participating) farmers.

The following constraints were identified in Sikasso: low soil fertility, high price of mineral fertilizers, iron toxicity, late weeding, low rice yields, non-compliance with cultural calendar, pest problems (stem borers, AfRGM, termites), disease problems (RYMV, neck blast), unavailability of good seed, lack of seed conservation methods, and lack of local names for improved varieties, leading to confusion in their use and dissemination.

In Niono, the constraints identified were low soil fertility, high price of mineral fertilizers, users' inadequate knowledge of chemical pesticide effects, no proper seed conservation method, problems on water management, lack of agricultural equipment, not following the cultural calendar, iron toxicity, and problems of pests (caseworms, AfRGM, stem borers) and diseases (RYMV).

Before the training, a majority of the farmers in Sikasso did not follow the cultural calendar (synchronous planting, crop rotation) and did not know any improved rice varieties and techniques (plowing, seedbed preparation, planting). After the training, a great number of farmers began using improved varieties, plant-based pesticides, mineral fertilizers, and improved techniques.

A striking observation at Sikasso was the greater participation of national agricultural research and extension systems and extension agents; they were seen interacting more frequently with farmers.

In Niono, the scenario was different. Many farmers already had regular contact with extension agents before and after the training. They knew improved rice varieties and had applied improved techniques and mineral fertilizers even before the training. The training only added to what they knew. However, the training afforded them the opportunity to appreciate the value of following a cultural calendar, using chemical pesticides judiciously, rotating nursery places, using organic fertilizers in addition to mineral ones, and using plant-based pesticides.

For the first time in both locations, farmers started putting down observations in their own field books (Fig. 1).

The crop yields of the trained farmers were higher than those of the untrained ones (Fig. 2). Rice yield increased by 2.0 t ha⁻¹ (36% increase) in the irrigated system and by 1.3 t ha⁻¹ in the rainfed lowland (93% increase). In the latter system, pest and disease problems decreased from 80% and 75%, respectively, before the training, to 16.6% and 36.6% after the training. In the irrigated system, these problems decreased from 60% and 80% before the training to 10% and 20% after.

In conclusion, these studies showed that farmers' pest management practices in Sikasso and Niono had undergone significant changes. Farmers have become so knowledgeable that they can now challenge agrochemical salesmen to prove the harmlessness of their products to target and nontarget organisms. It was suggested that

Fig. 1. Indicators to assess farmers' knowledge before and after training, Sikasso and Niono, Mali, 2004 wet season.

Fig. 2. Mean yields of participating and nonparticipating farmers, Sikasso and Niono, Mali, 2004 wet season.

this training has the potential to complement the extension delivery systems in Mali and therefore should be scaled up to cover larger groups of farmers.

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TAR-IVLP: an effective institutional mechanism for assessing the appropriateness of rice varieties

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Rice is cultivated under different types of production systems by farmers living in varied socio-economic and agroecological

conditions. Farmers' participation in technology assessment is essential in generating technologies suitable to their needs. The Tech-

nology Assessment and Refinement through Institution-Village Linkage Program (TAR-IVLP), promoted by the Indian Council